

Suppl. Table 2. The number swabs and EDCs analyzed with qPCR.

(A) The number of swabs															
Country	Farm	Litters	Treatment	Timepoint taken										Total:	
				2	3	5	7	14	21	28	42	56	70		
NLD	A	6	Placebo	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	22	238
NLD	A	6	Cocktail	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	23	239
NLD	B	5	Placebo	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21	210
NLD	B	6	Cocktail	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	300
NLD	C	6	Placebo	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	270
NLD	C	6	Cocktail	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	280
IRL	1	6	Placebo	21	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	31	300
IRL	1	6	Cocktail	33	23	33	33	33	33	33	33	33	33	33	320
IRL	2	6	Placebo	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	34	0	34	306
IRL	2	6	Cocktail	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	0	23	207
IRL	3	6	Placebo	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	350
IRL	3	6	Cocktail	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	300
Total per timepoint:				###	330	340	340	340	340	340	340	340	283	337	3320

(B) The number of EDCs																	
Country	Farm	Litters	Treatment	Timepoint placed											total:		
				-7	0	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63			
NLD	A	6	Placebo	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	5	65	
NLD	A	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	66	
NLD	B	5	Placebo	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	55	
NLD	B	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	66	
NLD	C	6	Placebo	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	3	63	
NLD	C	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	3	63	
IRL	1	6	Placebo	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	66	
IRL	1	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	66	
IRL	2	6	Placebo	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	1	1	1	1	41	
IRL	2	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	1	1	1	1	41	
IRL	3	6	Placebo	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	1	1	1	1	36	
IRL	3	6	Cocktail	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	1	1	1	1	36	
Total per timepoint:				71	71	71	71	71	71	71	61	51	51	51	51	44	664

Suppl. Table 2. Predictors from the Bayesian model of the odds ratio of *S. aureus* and *mecA* positivity between farms for both the Swabs, and EDCs.

		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>mecA</i>	
		Effect estimates inter farm variance	95% Credible Interval	Effect estimates inter farm variance	95% Credible Interval
Swabs	Ireland	24.78	4.71 to 11,731.11	42.1	3.25 to 24,100.79
	The Netherlands	106.7	3.94 to 1,202,604.28	992.27	12.93 to 51,649,961.08
EDCs	Ireland	3165.29	1.07 to 1.50*10 ²⁰	3.71	1.04 to 219.20
	The Netherlands	25.53	1.07 to 27,173.57	45251.9	24.05 to 17.92*10 ¹²